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GROUP KEY MANAGEMENT FOR SECURE WIRELESS MOBILE MULTICAST

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Abstract:

Addressing key management in mobile multicast communication is currently a booming topic due to the convergence of wireless and mobile technologies. With the proliferation of multiple group based services that are possible to co-exist within a single network, mobile subscribers could subscribe to these services concurrently while ubiquitous. However, the existing group key management (GKM) protocols intend to secure group communication for just a single group service. The GKM approaches involve inefficient use of keys and huge rekeying overheads, hence unsuitable for multiple multicast group environments. In this paper, we propose a novel GKM protocol for multiple multicast groups, called slot based multiple group key management (SMGKM) scheme. SMGKM supports the movement of single and multiple members across a homogeneous or heterogeneous wireless network while participating in multiple group services with minimized rekeying transmission overheads. Unlike conventional GKM protocols, SMGKM protocol can mitigate one-affect-n phenomenon, single point of failure and investment pressure of signalling load caused by rekeying at the core network. Numerical analysis and simulation results of the proposed protocol show significant resource economy in terms of communication bandwidth overhead, storage overheads at the Domain Key Distributor (DKD), mobile receiver and Area Key Distributors while providing intense security.

Index Terms: - Group key management, mobile multicast, security, wireless networks

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 OVERVIEW

MULTICAST is a bandwidth efficient technique for delivering group-oriented applications over the internet. These include applications such as video conferencing, interactive group games, video on demand (VoD), and mobile TV services. Multicast content distribution utilizes one-to-many and many-to-many transport communication mechanism. However the development of wireless networks and emergence of portable devices like smart phones, tablets has also increased to meet the demand for these multicast applications.

The evolving wireless networks such as WiMAX and 3GPP have standardized the multimedia broadcast/multicast service (MBMS). MBMS provide efficient delivery of broadcast and multicast services, both within a cell and within the core network. The evolved MBMS in Long Term Evolution (LTE) is a handy example.

However due to open access in wireless networks, the broadcasted multicast services over the air become vulnerable to various security attacks such as eavesdropping opportunities, Denial of service (DoS), physical node capture attacks, impersonation attacks and others.

To deliver the multicast content securely only to the group members in wireless networks, an access control mechanism which ensures confidentiality, safeguards digital contents, and simplifies accounting for the broadcasted services is obligatory. This becomes a vital requirement consequently; it is predictable that in the future, multiple multicast groups will co-exist within the same network due to the emergence of various group-based applications and computationally fast mobile devices along with increased data rates for next generation wireless networks.

Such a situation is probable to cause substantial key management overhead at the service provider (SP) for supporting multi-group services. Thus, the existing GKM schemes for secure wired and wireless mobile multicast networks will suffer from rekeying performance for cumulative multicast services because there are only targeted for a single multicast service. An example of a multi-service environment whereby members under different service groups (SG) subscribe to various set of multicast services.

II. RELATED WORKS

2.1 A NEW FUNDAMENTAL AND SECURE GROUP KEY MANAGEMENT APPROACH BASED ON LINEAR GEOMETRY

With a group controller GC using the theory of polynomial functions over a vector space over finite field is developed, where each member in the group corresponds to a vector in the vector space and the GC computes a central vector, whose inner product with every member's ID vector is identical. The central vector is published and each member can compute a common group key via inner product.

With the rapid expansion of Internet technology and the popularization of multicast, group-oriented applications, such as video conference, network games, and video on demand, etc., play more and more important roles. For the key management of secure group communication, there are many different approaches. In this paper, we will look the problem from a very different angle from before, namely a very fundamental mathematical point of view. From the theory of finite field, we know that this function must be a polynomial function, since every function over a field is a polynomial function.

2.2 A GROUP KEY MANAGEMENT APPROACH FOR MULTICAST CRYPTOSYSTEMS

The security in the multicast communication in the large groups is the major obstacles for effectively controlling access to the transmitting data. The IP Multicast itself does not provide any specific mechanisms to control the intruders in the group communication. Group key management is mainly addresses upon the trust model developed by Group Key Management Protocol (GKMP). There are several group key management protocols that

are proposed, this paper will however elaborate mainly on Group key management which has a sound scalability when compared with other central key management systems.

This paper emphasizes protocol which provides a scope for the dynamic group operations like join the group, leave the group, merge without the need of central mechanisms. The multicast group can be identified with the class D IP address so that the members can enter or leave the group with the management of Internet group management protocol. The trusted model gives a scope between the entities in a multicast security system. For secure group communication in the multicast network, a group key shared by all group members is required. The group key should be updated when there are membership changes in the group, such as when a new member joins or a current member leaves. Along with these considerations, we take the help relatively prime numbers and their enhancements that play a vital role in the construction of keys that enhances the strength for the security. Multicast cryptosystems are preferably for sending the messages to a specific group of members in the multicast group. Unicast is for one recipient to transfer the message and 'Broadcast' is to send the message to all the members in the network. Multicast applications have a vital role in enlarging and inflating of the Internet.

Another important feature of multicasting is its support for data casting applications. Instead of using a set of point-to-point connections between the participating nodes, multicasting can be used for distribution of the multimedia data to the receivers.

2.3 SECURE AND EFFICIENT KEY MANAGEMENT IN MOBILE AD HOC NETWORKS

In mobile ad hoc networks, due to unreliable wireless media, host mobility and lack of infrastructure, providing secure communications is a big challenge in this unique network environment. Usually cryptography techniques are used for secure communications in wired and wireless networks. The asymmetric cryptography is widely used because of its versatility (authentication, integrity, and confidentiality) and simplicity for key distribution.

However, this approach relies on a centralized framework of public key infrastructure (PKI). The symmetric approach has computation efficiency, yet it suffers from potential attacks on key agreement or key distribution. In fact, any cryptographic means is ineffective if the key management is weak. Key management is a central aspect for security in mobile ad hoc networks. In mobile ad hoc networks, the computational load and complexity for key management is strongly subject to restriction of the node's available resources and the dynamic nature of network topology. In this paper, we propose a secure and efficient key management framework (SEKM) for mobile ad hoc networks. SEKM builds PKI by applying a secret sharing scheme and an underlying multicast server group.

Mobile ad hoc networks are special type of wireless networks in which a collection of mobile hosts with wireless network interfaces may form a temporary network, without the aid of any fixed infrastructure or centralized administration.

In mobile ad hoc networks, nodes within their wireless transmitter ranges can communicate with each other directly (assume that all nodes have the same transmission range) while nodes outside the range have to rely on

some other nodes to relay messages. Thus a multi-hop scenario occurs, where the packets sent by the source host are relayed by several intermediate hosts before reaching the destination host.

2.4 MANAGING KEY MULTICASTING THROUGH ORTHOGONAL SYSTEMS

In this paper we propose a new protocol for Group Key Management. The protocol is based on the use of orthogonal systems in vector spaces. The main advantage in comparison to other existing multicast key management protocols consists in small communications overheads, i.e. length and number of messages to be sent, as well as key storage, especially with respect to a comparable security level. This makes the protocol especially attractive when the number of legitimate receivers is large. Traditional security measures are mainly applicable to a unicast environment, i.e. communications take place between two single parties. For instance, data confidentiality, one of the most important features in network security, can be offered in this environment by means of a pair of keys. However there exist many different situations where the usual secure unicast protocols cannot be used, mainly due to the nature of the information to be transmitted.

This usually happens when trying to deliver data from a sender to multiple receivers, especially when a huge amount of data needs to be delivered very quickly. In a typical situation users join and leave the group constantly.

There are a number of exciting multimedia applications that make good use of multicast capability, such as stock quote services, video-conferencing, pay-per-view TV, Internet radio, and so on. Many of the aforementioned multicast applications require security in data transmission, i.e., data can only be accessed or exchanged among an exclusive group of users. In the Pay-TV system, for example, the service providers usually employ Conditional Access System (CAS) to avoid unauthorized accessing of their video/audio streams, and only allow access to services based on payment. The natural approach to establish secure multicast communications is to agree on one or several symmetric encryption keys in order to encrypt messages. However, the key, or keys, must be renewed periodically to prevent outer or inner attacks. Depending on how key distribution and management are carried out, secure multicast schemes are divided into centralized, decentralized and distributed schemes. Centralized schemes depend directly on a single entity to distribute every cryptographic key.

III. SYSTEM ANALYSIS

3.1 EXISTING SYSTEM

. During the past decade a variety of group key management protocols have been proposed. Some of them are

- Diffie-Hellman key exchange. This protocol achieves secure and efficient key agreement in the context of dynamic peer groups which are relatively small and non-hierarchical. Their protocol is efficient only for small groups and not suitable for large groups.
- Secure group communications using key graphs. Drawback is computation complexity is high.
- An authenticated key management algorithm using extended Euclidean algorithm. Drawback is rekeying cost is high for batch joining and leaving operations and also communication complexity is high.

3.1.1 DRAWBACKS

- . Computation complexity is high
- Less confidentiality and security
- Storage complexity is high
- KS and group members computation complexity is high
- Rekeying cost is high for batch joining and leaving operations
- Communication complexity is high

3.2 PROPOSED SYSTEM

In multicast communication, messages are sent from one sender to a group of members. This is helpful for sending and exchanging private messages among group members.

Groups can be classified into static and dynamic groups. In static groups, membership of the group is predetermined and does not change during the communication. Therefore, the static approach distributes an unchanged group key (GK) to the members of the group when they join or leave from the multicast group. Moreover, they do not provide necessary solutions for changing the GK when the group membership changes which is not providing forward/backward secrecy.

When a new member joins into the service, it is the responsibility of the KS to prevent new members from having access to previous data. When an existing group member leaves from any group, he or she should not have further access to the multicast communication which provides forward secrecy. The backward and forward secrecy can be achieved only through the use of dynamic GK management schemes. In order to provide forward and backward secrecy, the keys are frequently updated whenever a member joins or leaves the multicast service. In this paper, we propose a new centralized GK management scheme based on the Chinese remainder theorem (CRT) to update and distribute the GK with less computational complexity to the multicast group members. In our proposed algorithm, the KS performs only one addition operation for updating the GK when a new user is joined in the dynamic multicast group. Similarly, it performs only one subtraction operation when an existing user is left from the multicast group.

3.2.2 ADVANTAGES OF PROPOSED SYSTEM

Some of the advantages of proposed system are:

- Allows to split large modules exponentiation
- Computational efforts can be reduced significantly
- Provides elegant numbering for sequence
- Efficient way to compute matrix exponentials
- Large range interpolation is a special case

IV. SYSTEM DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION MODELS

4.1 IMPLEMENTATION MODULES

The group key management for for secure wireless mobile multicast consists of four modules. They are:

- ❖ **Super Admin**
- ❖ **Group Admin**
- ❖ **Group Members**
- ❖ **User**

4.1.1 SUPER ADMIN

Super admin can create group, approve group admin, and also send message to every members in a group. As group-oriented applications become increasingly popular, the need for confidentiality of group communications also grows. While there are many mature secure protocols for peer-to-peer communication, the scenario for group communication with dynamically changing members is very different. Efficient agreement on a new group key after user join or leave is crucial to group communication confidentiality.

4.1.2 GROUP ADMIN

. Group admin can approve group members, and message to every members in a group. Group admin controls the individual group. Group admin can send confidential message to members with the help of 3D password, CRT and Elgamal generated keys.

4.1.3 GROUP MEMBERS

The third module is group member, who is the member of individual group. Group member can also send confidential message to members with the help of 3D password, CRT and Elgamal generated keys.

4.1.4 USER

The fourth module is the User. The user can send messages to all participants in the system but it is not confidential. The user can send request to join different groups.

4.2 SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig.4.2.1 Overall Architecture

V. CONCLUSION

In this system, we present centralized, simple and efficient CRT based group key management and Elgamal protocols for small to medium size dynamically changing groups. The simple nature of protocols together with minimal requirements on user computation and key storage space make them suitable for a variety of secure group communication. Even though evaluate group performance using some O-notations, the unit operations of this protocols (mainly XOR, addition, multiplication and modulo arithmetic) is different from most of other protocols

(mainly decryption, encryption and hashing) which can cause real performance results to be deviated. The future work will involve providing optimized implementation of this protocol to evaluate their real time performance and the comparison with other protocols.

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